
AN ADVANCE STUDY OF RECYCLED PP, HDPE AND PET FIBERS WITH THE APPLICATION OF MACHINE LEARNING TO ENHANCE CONCRETE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

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Abstract

With the rapid ongoing development of our cities, there is a need for alternative approaches to reusing recycled plastics. One of them could be to utilize them in the construction industry. This study aims to review the circular life cycle of plastic, its applications in various fields, and the compressive strength of concrete by mixing polypropylene (PP), high-density polyethylene (HDPE), and polyethylene terephthalate (PET). This review paper highlighted that with global plastic production reaching 400.3 Mt in 2022, dominated by PP (18.9%), PE-LD and PE-LLD (14.1%), and PVC (12.7%), there is an urgency for sustainable plastic management strategies. By examining the plastics' circular life cycle from the manufacturing process to the recycling process, Asia's projects to produce more than 200 Mt by 2060. This study investigates the varying properties like the Young's modulus of PP (1300 MPa), HDPE (1095 MPa), and PET (3500 MPa) and their influence on the behaviour of concrete. Additionally, incorporating these recycled fibers into concrete as a partial replacement of aggregate significantly improves the mechanical properties. For instance, HDPE fibers (up to 1.25%) demonstrate compressive strengths ranging between 23.3–40.1 MPa at 28–90 days, while PP fibers (0.5–1.5%) reach up to 90 MPa at 28 days. In addition, adding 1% of PET fibers also contributes positively to concrete performance, with the compressive strength of concrete reaching 38.60 MPa after 28 days of curing. This innovative approach offers three benefits, such as the waste reduction of plastic, the resistance of concrete to compression, and the cost of the material. Furthermore, the application Machine Learning (ML) techniques can improve concrete mix designs for strength and provide modeling tools to forecast plastic concrete's physical and mechanical properties. Finally, this study recommends further research, such as optimizing fiber content by combining different types of recycled plastic

fibers to maximize strength, establishing consumer performance analysis, or undertaking comprehensive life cycle assessments to advance sustainable construction practices and contribute to global waste reduction and climate change mitigation efforts.

1 Introduction

The pressing need to reduce waste—especially plastic waste—has gained international attention. According to (Jambeck et al., 2015), there are serious risks to human health, wildlife, and the ecosystem from plastic contamination. With an estimated 75–199 million tons of plastics in the ocean, the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) estimates that plastics make up about 85% of marine pollution (Litter, 2021). For instance, (Wilcox et al., 2015) highlights that more than 700 species are threatened by this pollution either by ingestion or entanglement. The rise in sustainable construction techniques has triggered a search for alternative materials such as recycled waste that will improve the performance of construction materials. Polystyrene terephthalate (PET), polypropylene (PP), and high-density polyethylene (HDPE) waste have been the subject of prior research, especially in the field of construction materials' engineering, where particular attention has been paid to their resilience and environmental friendliness.

PET is a synthetic thermoplastic polymer that is commonly used in packaging, textile fibers, and beverage containers (Hossain et al., 2024; Mwonga et al., 2022). Its high strength-to-weight ratio, chemical resistance, and thermal stability make it a desirable material for a variety of applications. When recycled and used as construction materials, PET fibers can improve mechanical qualities such as tensile strength and ductility, while also helping to reduce waste. On the other hand, PP is another useful synthetic polymer with excellent flexural strength and low density. It is very resistant to fatigue and chemical corrosion, making it useful for a variety of applications (Hwang et al., 2024). Indeed, previous experience showed that in construction, PP fibers can increase concrete's resistance to plastic shrinkage cracking and overall durability (Wang et al., 2019; Zhang & Zhao, 2012). Furthermore, HDPE has a high strength-to-density ratio and is resistant to a wide range of solvents. Its durability and moisture resistance make it useful in building applications (Li et al., 2024). When utilized as fibers in concrete, HDPE can improve flexural strength and crack resistance (Flores Nicolás et al., 2024).

Despite these developments, there is still a gap in understanding how to best use recycled plastic fibers in concrete through a comparative investigation of the performance of PET, PP, and HDPE fibers. In addition, there is a need to investigate the future projection of plastic production and analyze the life cycle from pre- to post-use. To address these research gaps, this study aims to evaluate the properties of PP, PET, and HDPE fibers, including their physical, mechanical, and chemical characteristics relevant in concrete applications; to investigate their uses; and to assess the compressive strength (f_c) of concrete reinforced with recycled PP, HDPE, or PET fibers by comparing their performance across different mix ratio design and forecasting their mechanical properties using Machine Learning (ML) algorithms.

Figure 1. Flow chart of concrete with PP, HDPE or PET fibers

Figure 2. Compressive strength after 7, 14, 28, 60, 90 days of 3 cement standard mortars (Jasiczak & Januszewski, 2019)

The scope of this study encompasses a comprehensive review of existing literature on the use of recycled PP, PET, and HDPE fibers in concrete. It analyzes data from multiple sources to provide a comparative assessment of the three fiber types. This research focuses on the mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced concrete, with particular emphasis on compressive strength. Additionally, the study investigates the potential of ML algorithms techniques such as multi-layer perceptron neural networks (MLPNN), artificial neural networks (ANN), support vector machines (SVM), decision trees (DT), and genetic engineering programming (GEP) to forecast the properties of concrete, including f_c (Althoey et al., 2022; Khan & Javed, 2023; Nafees et al., 2022).

2 Data and Methods

The procedure used to prepare the PP, PET or HDPE in concrete and the subsequent testing regime is depicted in Figure 1. Indeed, the process begins with the collection of recycled plastics, specifically PP, HDPE, and PET. The experimental work then proceeds through several key stages. First, researchers conduct physical and mechanical property tests on recycled plastics. Concurrently, they perform sand and gravel sieve analysis. The following step consists of determining the mixing design that will constitute the concrete. Researchers then prepare concrete samples, conducting slump tests to assess workability, and initiate the curing process. After a curing period of 7, 14, 28, and 90 days (estimate as the final curing), the concrete undergoes tests to determine its physical and mechanical properties, including the density, the bending strength, the bending stiffness, the tensile strength and the compressive strength. A typical illustration is demonstrated in Figure 2, where the compressive strength of cement increases rapidly in the first 7 days, with significant gains up to 28 days, and slower increases thereafter, reaching near-maximum strength by 90 days (Jasiczak & Januszewski, 2019).

Figure 3. (a) Global plastics production by polymer (Plastics, 2024b), (b) Plastic life cycle (Almeshal et al., 2020)

3 Recycled Plastic Production

The global production of plastic reached 400.3 million metric tons in 2022, as depicted in Figure 3(a). The findings of this survey indicate that Polypropylene (PP) accounts for the largest share of production, specifically 18.9%. This is followed by Low-density polyethylene (PE-LD and PE-LLD) at 14.1%, and Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) at 12.7%. Additionally, High-density and Medium-density polyethylene (PE-HD and PE-MD) make up 12.2% of the total, and Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) makes up 6.2% (Plastics, 2024b). Furthermore, Table 1 elucidates the depiction and utilization of repurposed plastic and their various implementations. PP is commonly utilized for storing containers, automobile components, and laboratory apparatus, whereas PET finds application in beverage bottles, food packaging, textile fibers, and carpeting.

Looking ahead to future perspective, Figure 3(b) depicts the cyclical nature of plastics from production to post use, highlighting the possibility of establishing a sustainable plastic economy (Almeshal et al., 2020). The cycle encompasses the stages of production, manufacturing, consumer utilization, and post-utilization management, which involve mechanical and chemical recycling, energy recovery, and reuse alternatives (Mirindi, 2024a; Yazdandoust & Mirindi, 2024). The objective of this method is to reduce the negative effects on the environment and optimize the use of resources. Moreover, the anticipated worldwide plastic output by region, as depicted in Figure 4, demonstrates substantial expansion and changes in geographical distribution from 2019 to 2060. Asia, excluding China and India, is projected to be the frontrunner in output growth, with China closely trailing behind. Europe and the United States are seeing modest growth, whereas India, Sub-Saharan Africa, and the Middle East & North Africa are undergoing significant increase from smaller starting points (Worldindata, 2024). The high occurrence of PP, HDPE, and PET waste in worldwide manufacturing offers the possibility to utilize them as fibers to partially replace the aggregates in concrete. Undoubtedly, with the ongoing increase in global plastic manufacturing, incorporating these elements into concrete presents a significant opportunity for reducing waste and enhancing infrastructure.

Figure 4. Projected global plastic by region (2019 – 2060), own elaboration based on (Worldindata, 2024)

Type of Plastic	Description	Common uses
High-density polyethylene (HDPE)	Durable, opaque plastic	Recycling bins, detergent containers, outdoor furniture, agricultural piping, pallets
Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)	Clear, strong plastic or fiber	Beverage bottles, food packaging, textile fibers, carpeting
Low-density polyethylene (LDPE)	Flexible, translucent plastic	Construction films, packaging materials, agricultural sheeting
Plasticized polyvinyl chloride (PPVC)	Pliable, transparent plastic	Flooring, hose linings, inflatable products
Unplasticized polyvinyl chloride (UPVC)	Rigid, durable plastic	Plumbing fixtures, window frames, outdoor decking
Polypropylene (PP)	Versatile, semi-rigid plastic	Storage containers, automotive parts, laboratory equipment
Polystyrene (PS)	Rigid, brittle plastic	Office supplies, CD cases, disposable cutlery
Expanded polystyrene (EPS)	Lightweight foam	Insulation, protective packaging, construction materials
Epoxies (EP)	Thermoset polymer	Adhesives, coatings, electronic components
Thermoplastic Elastomers (TPE)	Rubber-like plastic	Footwear, automotive parts, medical devices
Polyamides (PA) / Nylon	Strong, abrasion-resistant	Textiles, automotive components, industrial parts
High Impact Polystyrene (HIPS)	Tough, opaque plastic	Appliance parts, packaging, toys
Polycarbonate (PC)	Transparent, impact-resistant	Safety equipment, electronic housings, automotive components
Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS)	Tough, heat-resistant	Electronic enclosures, automotive trim, pipe systems

Table 1. Recycled plastic description and application (Hopewell et al., 2009; Plastics, 2024a; Ragaert et al., 2017)

4 Characteristics properties of PP, PET and HDPE

Table 1 provides a comprehensive overview of the physical and mechanical properties of virgin and recycled polypropylene (PP), high-density polyethylene (HDPE), and polyethylene terephthalate (PET).

The density of recycled plastic according to ASTM D1505 (Oster & Yamamoto, 1963) or ASTM D792 (ASTMD792-98, 1991) is calculated as follows:

$$\rho (g/cm^3) = \frac{m}{V} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is density, m is mass, and V is volume. Alternatively, specific gravity can be determined and converted to density using the formula: Specific Gravity = (Weight of sample in air) / (Weight of sample in air - Weight of sample in water), with density then calculated as:

$$\rho = \text{Specific gravity} \times 0.9975 \text{ g/cm}^3 \quad (2)$$

The melting point is typically determined using Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) following ASTM D3418 or ISO 11357 (Zubair et al., 2017). Tensile strength and elongation at break are measured using ASTM D638 or ISO 527 (Thackeray & Hinkley, 2022), where tensile strength equals maximum load divided by original cross-sectional area, and elongation at break is calculated as a percentage of change in gauge length.

Flexural modulus or the Modulus of Elasticity (MOE), determined by ASTM D790 or ISO 178, is calculated using the equation (Mirindi, 2024a):

$$MOE (MPa) = \frac{L^3 \times m}{4 \times b \times d^3} \quad (3)$$

where L is supporting span, m is the slope of the load-deflection curve, and b and d are specimen dimensions.

Young's modulus is derived from the stress-strain curve in tensile testing or compression (Figure 5) (Sciencenotes, 2024), calculated as stress divided by strain in the linear portion as depicted this equation:

$$E (MPa) = \frac{\sigma}{\epsilon} = (F/A) / (\Delta L/L_0) = F L_0 / A \Delta L = mg L_0 / \pi r^2 \Delta L \quad (4)$$

where E is Young's modulus; σ is the uniaxial stress (tensile or compressive), which is force per cross sectional area; ϵ is the strain, which is the change in length per original length; F is the force of compression or extension; A is the cross-sectional surface area or the cross-section perpendicular to

Figure 5. Young's modulus which is a modulus of elasticity equal to the compressive stress divided by the axial strain (Sciencenotes, 2024)

the applied force; ΔL is the change in length (negative under compression; positive when stretched); L_0 is the original length; g is the acceleration due to gravity; and r is the radius of a cylindrical wire.

Lastly, melt flow index (MFI) is measured using ASTM D1238 or ISO 1133 (Aisa et al., 2024), with the formula:

$$MFI(g/10\ min) = \frac{m \times 600}{t} \quad (5)$$

Where m is the mass of extruded polymer and t is the time interval in seconds.

(Noor Hasanah et al., 2014) report that virgin PP has a density range of 0.898-0.920 g/cm³, melting points between 135-165°C, and tensile strengths of 25-33 MPa. Recycled PP shows slightly lower values, with densities around 0.897-0.900 g/cm³, a melting point of 141°C, and tensile strengths of 16.1-24 MPa. HDPE, as studied by (Olam, 2023) and (Kusuktham & Teeranachaideekul, 2014), demonstrates a higher density range (0.9-1.0 g/cm³) compared to PP, with melting points between 110-140°C and tensile strengths of 15-20 MPa. PET, according to (Olam, 2023) and (Alshammari et al., 2022), stands out with the highest density (1.38-1.56 g/cm³) and melting point (245-250°C) among the three plastics. It also exhibits the highest tensile strength (40-60 MPa), but lower elongation at break (6.3-46%) compared to PP and HDPE. PET's flexural modulus (2000-3500 MPa) and Young's modulus (1000-3500 MPa) are significantly higher than the other plastics, indicating greater stiffness. These variations in properties influence the plastics' behavior when used as fibers or aggregates in concrete, affecting the workability, strength, and durability of the resulting composite material. The data suggests that recycled plastics maintain many of the desirable properties of their virgin counterparts, supporting their potential use in concrete applications.

Material	Chemical structure	Density (g/cm ³)	Melting Point (°C)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elongation at Break (%)	Flexural Modulus (MPa)	Young's Modulus (MPa)	MFI (g/10 min)	Reference
Virgin PP	(CH ₃) _n	-	-	34.5	300	1380	-	-	(Noor Hasanah et al., 2014)
Virgin PP		0.901 - 0.905	164	25 - 33	-	1103 - 1344	-	0.6 - 0.7	(Noor Hasanah et al., 2014)
Virgin PP		0.898 - 0.920	135 - 165	-	-	-	1100 - 1300	-	(Noor Hasanah et al., 2014)
Recycled PP		0.900	-	16.1	-	700	700	2.14	(Noor Hasanah et al., 2014)
Recycled PP		0.897	141	24	-	850	-	0.5 - 1.3	(Noor Hasanah et al., 2014)
HDPE	(C ₂ H ₄) _n	0.970	134	15 - 20	53	904	1095	-	(Olam, 2023)
HDPE		0.9 - 1.0	110 - 140	15.66 - 17.57	21.11 - 53.75	-	-	6	(Kusuktham & Teeranachaid-eekul, 2014)
PET	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄	1.38 - 1.56	248 - 250	40 - 60	19 - 46	2000 - 3500	1000 - 3500	-	(Olam, 2023)
PET		0.89	245	45.8 ± 2.3	6.3 ± 1.9	-	-	-	(Alshammari et al., 2022)

Table 2. Characteristic properties of polypropylene (PP), polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and high-density polyethylene (HDPE)

Results and discussion

The utilization of recycled PP, PET, and HDPE fibers as partial replacements for aggregates in concrete has shown promising results in enhancing compressive strength (f_c), as evidenced by Table 3. This innovative approach not only addresses the growing concern of plastic waste management, but also contributes to the development of more sustainable construction materials. The data reveals that the incorporation of these plastic fibers, typically ranging from 0.5% to 2% by weight of cement or as a partial replacement of fine aggregates, can significantly influence concrete's compressive strength

according to ASTM C39 (Standard Test Method for Compressive Strength of Cylindrical Concrete Specimens), using the formula as follows:

$$f_c(\text{MPa}) = \frac{P}{A} \quad (6)$$

where f_c is the compressive strength, P the maximum load (N) and A is the area of specimen (mm^2) (ASTMC39, 2012).

As demonstrated in the results, HDPE fibers at concentrations up to 1.25% have demonstrated compressive strengths ranging from 23.3 to 40.1 MPa at 28 and 90 days, respectively (Pešić et al., 2016). Similarly, PP fibers at 0.5-1.5% inclusion rates have shown remarkable strength improvements, reaching up to 90 MPa at 28 days (Małek et al., 2020). PET fibers, while generally showing lower strength enhancements compared to PP and HDPE, still contribute positively to concrete performance, with strengths up to 30 MPa at 28 days for 0.5-2.0% inclusion rates (Nkomo et al., 2022). These results underscore the potential of recycled plastic fibers to not only serve as a sustainable alternative to traditional aggregates, but also to enhance the mechanical properties of concrete, offering a dual benefit of waste reduction and improved construction material performance.

Type of plastic fiber	Mix proportion					Compressive Strength (MPa)				References
	Cement (kg/m^3)	Fine aggregate (kg/m^3)	Coarse aggregate (kg/m^3)	Plastic (%)	Plastic (kg/m^3)	7 days	14 days	28 days	90 days	
HDPE	320	721.3 - 848.6	1029.23 - 1286.5	-	< 257.308]15, 25[]22, 30[]25, 35[-	(Shanmugapriya & Santhi, 2017)
HDPE	380	780	860	< 1.25	-	-	-]23.3, 33.2[]37.2, 40.1[(Pešić et al., 2016)
PET	330.65	752.85	962.45 - 1013.10	-	28.98 – 57.96	-	-	15.30 - 25.28	-	(Aocharoen & Chotickai, 2023)
HDPE	330.65	439.94 - 676.80	1013.1	-	28.98 – 86.93	-	-	17.97 - 26.43	-	(Aocharoen & Chotickai, 2023)
HDPE	-	-	-	2- 8	-]9.4, 12.6[]10.3, 16.1[]14.7, 30.6[-	(Kodua et al., 2018)
HDPE	360	630	1330]0.25, 1,0[]0.90, 3.60[]14, 24[-]24, 33[]37, 48[(Anum & Job, 2021)

HDPE	430	570	1330	<1]1.08, 4.30[]35, 45[]43, 55[]42, 65[(Anum & Job, 2021)
PP	550	-	-	0.5 - 1.5	2.75 - 8.25]20, 80[]45, 80[]50, 90[(Małek et al., 2020)
PP	426	642	905	0.5 - 1.0]25.1– 29.63[-]33.00 - 38.60[-	(Das et al., 2018)
PET	346.5	519.75	1093.5	0.5 - 2.0	9.93 – 39.74	-	-]10, 30[-	(Nkomo et al., 2022)

Table 3. Compressive strength of recycled plastic fibers in concrete

6 Machine Learning Algorithms

Machine learning (ML) algorithms have shown great potential in predicting the compressive strength of concrete containing recycled plastics like polypropylene (PP), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and high-density polyethylene (HDPE). These algorithms can optimize concrete mix designs to maximize strength while creating modelling tools for estimating the f_c of plastic concrete (Nafees et al., 2022). Some commonly used ML algorithms for forecasting strength include:

- Multi-layer Perceptron Neural Networks (MLPNN): MLPNNs are feedforward Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) that map input data to outputs through multiple layers of interconnected nodes (Mirindi et al., 2024). The output of each node is calculated using an activation function, such as the sigmoid function:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (7)$$

x represents the weighted sum of the inputs to a node, i.e., $x = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i$, where w_i is the weight of the i_{th} input, x_i is the i_{th} input value, and b is the bias term.

- Artificial Neural Networks (ANN): ANNs are inspired by biological neural networks and consist of input, hidden, and output layers (Figure 6). They learn through backpropagation, adjusting weights and biases to minimize the error between predicted and actual outputs (Mirindi, 2024b). The output of a neuron is given by:

$$y = f\left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b\right) \quad (8)$$

y is the output of a neuron, f is the activation function, w_i is the weight of the i_{th} input, x_i is the i_{th} input value, n is the total number of inputs, and b is the bias term.

Figure 6. Typical neural network architecture (Nafees et al., 2022)

Figure 7. SVMs Optimize Margin Between Support Vectors or Classes (Spiceworks, 2024)

- Support Vector Machines (SVM): SVMs are supervised learning models that find the hyperplane that maximally separates different classes in a high-dimensional space (Figure 7). The decision function is:

$$f(x) = \text{sign} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i \alpha_i k(x_i, x) + b \right) \quad (9)$$

where x_i are the support vectors (training examples closest to the decision boundary), y_i are the corresponding class labels (± 1), α_i are the learned weights, k is the kernel function that measures similarity between x_i and the input vector x , b is the bias term, and sign is the signum function that outputs +1 or -1 based on the sign of the argument.

- Decision Trees (DT) classification algorithm: DTs are hierarchical models that make predictions by traversing a tree structure based on input features as depicted in Figure 8. At each node, the feature that best splits the data is chosen using criteria like information gain or Gini impurity.
- Genetic Programming (GP): GP evolves computer programs or mathematical expressions to solve a problem. It uses genetic operators such as crossover and mutation to optimize solutions. A GP individual can represent a formula for concrete strength prediction.

7 Conclusion

The integration of recycled PP, HDPE, and PET fibers as partial replacements for aggregates in concrete has demonstrated significant potential for enhancing concrete's compressive strength, while also addressing critical environmental concerns. This innovative approach offers a dual benefit of waste reduction and improved construction material performance. This research highlighted that the global plastic production reached 400.3 Mt in 2022, with PP leading at 18.9%, followed by PE-LD and PE-LLD at 14.1%, and PVC at 12.7%. Additionally, the projected global plastic production by region from 2019 to 2060 shows Asia (excluding China and India) leading the increase, followed closely by China, with Europe and the Americas showing moderate growth. This trend underscores the urgency

Figure 8. Flow chart of decision tree (Javapoint, 2024)..

of sustainable plastic management strategies by producing plastics, followed by using them, collecting and recycling the waste plastics, and reusing them for environmental, cost-, and strength-related purposes for construction materials such as concrete.

Furthermore, the circular life cycle of plastics, from production to post-use management, emphasizes the potential for a sustainable plastic economy using recycled PP, HDPE, and PET fibers. Common uses for these recycled plastics include storage containers, packaging materials, and construction applications. The varying properties of PP (density 0.898-0.920 g/cm³, melting point 135-165°C), HDPE (density 0.9-1.0 g/cm³, melting point 110-140°C), and PET (density 1.38-1.56 g/cm³, melting point 245-250°C) influence their behavior in concrete, affecting workability, strength, and durability. This study reveals that incorporating these recycled plastic fibers, typically at 0.5% to 2% in the concrete mix design, can substantially influence concrete's mechanical properties. HDPE fibers at concentrations up to 1.25% have shown compressive strengths ranging from 23.3 and 33.2 to 37.2 and 40.1 MPa at 28 and 90 days, respectively, while PP fibers at 0.5-1.5% inclusion rates have exhibited remarkable strength improvements, reaching up to 90 MPa at 28 days. Additionally, the incorporation of PET fibers ranging between 28.98 and 57.96 kg/m³ still contributes positively to concrete performance, with values ranging between 15.30 to 25.28 MPa after 28 days of curing.

Finally, this study investigates the application of ML algorithms such as DT, MLPNN, SVM, and RF. These algorithms could further improve the efficiency of concrete mix designs by maximizing strength and developing modeling tools for predicting the physical and mechanical characteristics of plastic concrete, including f_c . This research not only presents a viable solution for plastic waste management, but also contributes to the development of more sustainable and resilient construction materials. The utilization of recycled plastic fibers in concrete aligns with circular economy principles, offering a pathway to reduce the environmental impact of both the construction and plastic industries, while potentially lowering construction costs using recycled materials.

This research review recommends future research areas, including:

- Optimizing fiber content and combinations: Investigate the synergistic effects of combining different types of recycled plastic fibers to maximize strength and durability improvements.

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- Consumer performance analysis: Evaluate the real-world performance and user satisfaction of structures built with recycled plastic fiber-reinforced concrete to assess its practical viability and market acceptance.
 - Standardization efforts: Develop industry standards and guidelines for the incorporation of recycled plastic fibers in concrete to ensure consistent quality and performance. Propose a standardized mix design for manufacturing companies to facilitate widespread adoption and quality control.
 - Life cycle assessment: Perform comprehensive life cycle assessments to quantify the environmental benefits and potential drawbacks of using recycled plastic fibers in concrete compared to traditional materials.

These recommendations aim to advance the field towards more sustainable construction practices, contributing to global efforts in waste reduction, resource efficiency, and climate change mitigation.

References

- Aisa, N. N., Setiawan, R., Wicaksono, D., & Dimas, E. (2024). The effect of recycling frequency on the melt flow rate of polypropylene materials. *AIP Conference Proceedings*,
- Almeshal, I., Tayeh, B. A., Alyousef, R., Alabduljabbar, H., Mohamed, A. M., & Alaskar, A. (2020). Use of recycled plastic as fine aggregate in cementitious composites: A review. *Construction and Building Materials*, *253*, 119146.
- Alshammari, B. A., Hossain, M., Alenad, A. M., Alharbi, A. G., & AlOtaibi, B. M. (2022). Experimental and theoretical analysis of mechanical properties of graphite/polyethylene terephthalate nanocomposites. *Polymers*, *14*(9), 1718.
- Althoey, F., Amin, M. N., Khan, K., Usman, M. M., Khan, M. A., Javed, M. F., Sabri, M. M. S., Alrowais, R., & Maglad, A. M. (2022). Machine learning based computational approach for crack width detection of self-healing concrete. *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, *17*, e01610.
- Anum, I., & Job, O. F. (2021). Compressive Strength Characteristics of Concrete Modified with Treated High-Density Polyethylene. *CSID Journal of Infrastructure Development*, *4*(1), 112-121.
- Aocharoen, Y., & Chotickai, P. (2023). Compressive mechanical and durability properties of concrete with polyethylene terephthalate and high-density polyethylene aggregates. *Cleaner Engineering and Technology*, *12*, 100600.
- ASTMC39. (2012). ASTM C39. Standard Test Method for Compressive Strength of Cylindrical Concrete Specimens. In: Standard, ASTM International West Conshohocken.
- ASTMD792-98. (1991). Standard test methods for density and specific gravity (relative density) of plastics by displacement.
- Das, C. S., Dey, T., Dandapat, R., Mukharjee, B. B., & Kumar, J. (2018). Performance evaluation of polypropylene fibre reinforced recycled aggregate concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, *189*, 649-659.
- Flores Nicolás, A., Menchaca Campos, E. C., Flores Nicolás, M., Martínez González, J. J., González Noriega, O. A., & Uru-churtu Chavarín, J. (2024). Influence of Recycled High-Density Polyethylene Fibers on the Mechanical and Electrochemical Properties of Reinforced Concrete. *Fibers*, *12*(3), 24.
- Hopewell, J., Dvorak, R., & Kosior, E. (2009). Plastics recycling: challenges and opportunities. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *364*(1526), 2115-2126.

- Hossain, M. T., Shahid, M. A., Mahmud, N., Darda, M. A., & Samad, A. B. (2024). Techniques, applications, and prospects of recycled polyethylene terephthalate bottle: a review. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 37(3), 1268-1286.
- Hwang, I.-T., Kim, M.-B., Sohn, J.-Y., Shin, J., Seo, H.-S., Ji, H.-J., Jeong, S.-Y., Bae, S., Shin, K., & Jung, C.-H. (2024). Green and efficient radiation-based preparation of crosslinked poly (vinyl pyrrolidone)-iodine (PVP-I)-introduced polypropylene (PP) sheets for antibacterial wound dressing application. *European Polymer Journal*, 208, 112848.
- Jambeck, J. R., Geyer, R., Wilcox, C., Siegler, T. R., Perryman, M., Andrady, A., Narayan, R., & Law, K. L. (2015). Plastic waste inputs from land into the ocean. *science*, 347(6223), 768-771.
- Jasiczak, J., & Januszewski, M. (2019). Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of a Steel–Cement Mortar Interface Zone in Concrete Modified with Mineral Additives and Chemical Admixtures. IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering.
- Javapoint. (2024). <https://www.javatpoint.com/machine-learning-decision-tree-classification-algorithm>.
- Khan, M., & Javed, M. F. (2023). Towards sustainable construction: Machine learning based predictive models for strength and durability characteristics of blended cement concrete. *Materials Today Communications*, 37, 107428.
- Kodua, J., Tagbor, T., Berko-Boateng, V., & Appiah, K. (2018). Influence of recycled waste high density polyethylene plastic aggregate on the physico-chemical and mechanical properties of concrete.
- Kusuktham, B., & Teeranachaideekul, P. (2014). Mechanical properties of high density polyethylene/modified calcium silicate composites. *Silicon*, 6, 179-189.
- Li, X., Mahadas, N. A., Zhang, M., DePodesta, J., Stefik, M., & Tang, C. (2024). Sustainable high-density polyethylene via chemical recycling: From modification to polymerization methods. *Polymer*, 126698.
- Litter, A. G. A. O. M. (2021). From Pollution To Solution.
- Małek, M., Jackowski, M., Łasica, W., & Kadela, M. (2020). Characteristics of recycled polypropylene fibers as an addition to concrete fabrication based on portland cement. *Materials*, 13(8), 1827.
- Mirindi, D. (2024a). A Review of Particleboard Development and Performance Using Non-Toxic and Biodegradable Adhesives. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, 72(5), 252-260. <https://doi.org/10.14445/22315381/IJETT-V72I5P126>
- Mirindi, D. (2024b). A Review of the Advances in Artificial Intelligence in Transportation System Development.
- Mirindi, D., Sanders, T. N., Oshineye, O., & Hunter, J. (2024). Integration of Artificial Intelligence and Smart Technologies in Offsite Construction: A Comprehensive Review. *Transforming Construction with Off-site Methods and Technologies*.
- Mwonga, M. M., Kabubo, C., & Gathimba, N. (2022). Properties of concrete produced using surface modified polyethylene terephthalate fibres. *Civil Engineering Journal*, 8(06).
- Nafees, A., Khan, S., Javed, M. F., Alrowais, R., Mohamed, A. M., Mohamed, A., & Vatin, N. I. (2022). Forecasting the mechanical properties of plastic concrete employing experimental data using machine learning algorithms: DT, MLPNN, SVM, and RF. *Polymers*, 14(8), 1583.
- Nkomo, N., Masu, L., & Nziu, P. (2022). Effects of polyethylene terephthalate fibre reinforcement on mechanical properties of concrete. *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, 2022(1), 4899298.
- Noor Hasanah, T., Wijeyesekera, D., bin Bakar, I., & Saidin, W. (2014). New lightweight construction material: cellular mat using recycled plastic. *Key Engineering Materials*, 594, 503-510.
- Olam, M. (2023). Mechanical and thermal properties of HDPE/PET microplastics, applications, and impact on environment and life. In *Advances and Challenges in Microplastics*. IntechOpen.
- Oster, G., & Yamamoto, M. (1963). Density Gradient Techniques. *Chemical Reviews*, 63(3), 257-268.

-
- Pešić, N., Živanović, S., Garcia, R., & Papastergiou, P. (2016). Mechanical properties of concrete reinforced with recycled HDPE plastic fibres. *Construction and Building Materials*, *115*, 362-370.
- Plastics. (2024a). <https://plasticseurope.org/>.
- Plastics. (2024b). <https://plasticseurope.org/knowledge-hub/plastics-the-fast-facts-2023/>.
- Ragaert, K., Delva, L., & Van Geem, K. (2017). Mechanical and chemical recycling of solid plastic waste. *Waste management*, *69*, 24-58.
- Sciencenotes. (2024). <https://sciencenotes.org/youngs-modulus-formula-and-example/>.
- Shanmugapriya, M., & Santhi, H. (2017). Strength and chloride permeable properties of concrete with high density polyethylene wastes. *Int. J. Chem. Sci*, *15*(1), 10-17.
- Spiceworks. (2024). <https://www.spiceworks.com/tech/big-data/articles/what-is-support-vector-machine/>.
- Thackeray, K., & Hinkley, J. (2022). Mechanical Testing and Properties of Plastics—An Introduction.
- Wang, J., Dai, Q., Si, R., & Guo, S. (2019). Mechanical, durability, and microstructural properties of macro synthetic polypropylene (PP) fiber-reinforced rubber concrete. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, *234*, 1351-1364.
- Wilcox, C., Van Seville, E., & Hardesty, B. D. (2015). Threat of plastic pollution to seabirds is global, pervasive, and increasing. *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences*, *112*(38), 11899-11904.
- Worldindata. (2024). <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/global-plastics-production>.
- Yazdandoust, F., & Mirindi, D. (2024). Rethinking Sustainability: Towards An Open System Approach.
- Zhang, S., & Zhao, B. (2012). Influence of polypropylene fibre on the mechanical performance and durability of concrete materials. *European Journal of Environmental and Civil Engineering*, *16*(10), 1269-1277.
- Zubair, U., Ahmad, S., Rasheed, A., Afzal, A., & Ahmad, F. (2017). Polymer Testing Methods for Conventional and Technical Textiles. In *Advanced Textile Testing Techniques* (pp. 13-54). CRC Press.

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